

Continuation Analysis for Identifying Bifurcations in Dynamical Systems: Nonlinear Dynamics Seminar Report WS2022-23

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1 Dynamical Systems

A dynamical system is a system that evolve with time according to a set of predefined rules. Dynamical systems are ubiquitous ranging from brain activity, collective behavior of organisms, population growth, climate, to motion of celestial bodies. The state of a system at any given timepoint can be represented as a collection of the state variables $\mathbf{x} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_D\}$. For example, the state of a system may constitute the membrane potential in a neuron, position and orientation of each organism in a group, or temperature and pressure in a weather system. The space spanned by the state variables is known as state space \mathcal{S} with dimension D .

Dynamical systems can be classified as discrete or continuous based on the nature of time in which the dynamical system evolve. A discrete dynamical system is given by

$$\mathbf{x}_{n+1} = f(\mathbf{x}_n) \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x}_n is the state of the system at timepoint n , \mathbf{x}_{n+1} is the state of the system at timepoint $n + 1$, and f is the dynamic rule that maps the current state \mathbf{x}_n to the next state \mathbf{x}_{n+1} . Here the time in which the dynamic system evolves is discrete which means that we access the state of the system at discrete time intervals. For example, we measure the temperature and pressure of a weather system once every day, or we measure the position and orientation of a group of animals only every minute and so on. Although the system might change its behavior between two discrete timepoints n and $n + 1$, the dynamical rule would only specify the state of the system in the next timepoint irrespective of the path taken by the system to reach that state.

On the other hand, in a continuous dynamical system, given by

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dt} = f(\mathbf{x}), \quad (2)$$

the time in which the dynamical system evolve is continuous. Here the dynamical rule f gives the rate of change of the state x rather than the next state itself.

In both discrete and continuous dynamical systems, When the dynamical rule f is independent of time, it is called an autonomous dynamical system (in contrast to nonautonomous dynamical systems in which f depends on time). If the dynamical rule f does not have any stochastic elements, the system is a deterministic dynamical system and if the rule f consists of nonlinear relations of state variables, it specifies a nonlinear dynamical system.

2 Fixed points and linearized stability analysis

A fixed point \mathbf{x}^* is a state of a dynamical system that does not change in time [Datseris and Parlitz, 2022]. In a discrete dynamical system, a fixed point is defined by $f(\mathbf{x}^*) = \mathbf{x}^*$, whereas in a continuous dynamical

system, it is given by $f(\mathbf{x}^*) = 0$. If we apply a small perturbation to a system which is at its fixed point dies down and the system eventually returns back to the fixed point, we call it a stable fixed point. On the other hand, if the perturbation grows and takes the system away from the fixed point, we call it an unstable fixed point.

For a continuous dynamical system, one can mathematically formulate the evolution of an infinitesimal perturbation ϵ to a dynamical system at fixed point \mathbf{x}^* using Taylor expansion up to linear terms as [Datseris and Parlitz, 2022]

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}|_{\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}^*+\epsilon} = f(\mathbf{x}^* + \epsilon) = f(\mathbf{x}^*) + J_f(\mathbf{x}^*) \cdot \epsilon \quad (3)$$

where $J_f(\mathbf{x}^*)$ is the Jacobian of f at fixed point \mathbf{x}^* given by

$$J_f(\mathbf{x}^*) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_1} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_D} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial f_D}{\partial x_1} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_D}{\partial x_D} \end{bmatrix}_{\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}^*} \quad (4)$$

Since $f(\mathbf{x}^*) = 0$, we can rewrite Eqn. 3 as

$$\dot{\epsilon} = J_f(\mathbf{x}^*) \cdot \epsilon. \quad (5)$$

Eqn. 5 is called linearized dynamics and sufficiently approximates the evolution of the dynamical system very close to the fixed point \mathbf{x}^* . The stability of the fixed point \mathbf{x}^* is then characterized by the eigenvalues of the Jacobian $J_f(\mathbf{x}^*)$ given by $\{\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_D\}$. For this, one can write the evolution of the perturbation ϵ near the fixed point \mathbf{x}^* , in terms of the eigenvalues $\mu_i, i = 1..D$ and eigenvectors $\mathbf{e}_i, i = 1..D$ of the Jacobian $J_f(\mathbf{x}^*)$ as [Datseris and Parlitz, 2022]

$$\epsilon(t) = \sum_{i=1}^D c_i \mathbf{e}_i e^{(\mu_i t)} \quad (6)$$

The real part of the eigenvalue μ_i specifies the rate of growth or decay of the perturbation along the i -th eigenvector \mathbf{e}_i and the imaginary part (if one exists, it will always exist in complex-conjugate pairs) specifies a rotation in the plane spanned by two eigenvectors with complex-conjugate eigenvalues. A fixed point \mathbf{x}^* is stable if the perturbation $\epsilon(t)$ decays in all directions, that is the real part of all eigenvalues are less than 0. If the real part of at least one of the eigenvalues is greater than zero, the perturbation would grow in that direction and thus the fixed point \mathbf{x}^* is unstable. If any of the eigenvalues have a zero real part, the stability of the fixed point \mathbf{x}^* depends on higher-order terms of the Taylor expansion in Eqn. 3.

For a 1D dynamical system, Eqn. 5 reduces to $\dot{\epsilon} = f'(x)|_{x=x^*} \cdot \epsilon$, where $f'(x)|_{x=x^*}$ specifies the slope of $f(x)$ at $x = x^*$ and time evolution of perturbation ϵ is given by $\epsilon(t) = \epsilon e^{(f'(x)t)|_{x=x^*}}$. The fixed point x^* is stable if $f'(x) < 0$ at $x = x^*$ (slope of $f(x)$ at $x = x^*$ is negative) and unstable if $f'(x) > 0$ at $x = x^*$ (slope of $f(x)$ at $x = x^*$ is positive).

3 Bifurcations

Bifurcations are significant, qualitative changes in the system's behavior as a result of change in the parameters [Datseris and Parlitz, 2022]. For example, a fixed point changes its stability or new fixed points or limit cycles are born. The parameter values at which a bifurcation occur are known as critical points or bifurcation points. Some of the most common bifurcations ¹ in continuous dynamical systems are presented in Fig. 1.

¹The bifurcations that we discuss here are local bifurcations in the sense that the bifurcation occurs at a single point in the state space. In contrast, global bifurcations results in changes in topology of the trajectories that are not restricted to a small neighborhood. An example of a global bifurcation is the homoclinic bifurcation where a limit cycle collides with a saddle node and vanishes. For a more detailed overview on local and global bifurcations, see [Datseris and Parlitz, 2022]

Figure 1: Examples of some of the typical bifurcations in dynamical systems and their functional form f for a one-dimensional system which exhibits these bifurcations. Bifurcation diagrams are shown in the bottom row which shows the value of fixed points and their stability as a function of parameter p . Stable fixed points are denoted by solid line and unstable fixed points by dotted line. Hopf bifurcation occurs in two- or more dimensional systems and in the example in (d), $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{Z}$ and i denotes the imaginary part. Figure reused from [Datseris and Parlitz, 2022].

In saddle-node bifurcation as shown in Fig. 1a, for values of $p < 0$, there exists no fixed point since $f(x)$ is not zero for any x . However, at $p = 0$, a saddle-node fixed point occurs at $x = 0$ (perturbations on one side of x grows and other side decays). For $p > 0$, two fixed points occur at $x = \pm\sqrt{p}$, one of which is stable and the other is unstable. In transcritical bifurcation (Fig. 1b), two existing fixed points at $x = 0$ and $x = p$ exchange their stability properties at the bifurcation point $p = 0$. In a pitchfork bifurcation (Fig. 1c), the fixed point at $x = 0$ changes its stability at the bifurcation point $p = 0$, and two new fixed points emerge with same stability properties. When the existing fixed point becomes unstable and two stable fixed points are created, it is called a supercritical pitchfork bifurcation. When a previously unstable fixed point becomes stable and two new unstable fixed points arise, it is a subcritical pitchfork bifurcation. Hopf bifurcations (Fig. 1d) occur in dynamical systems which are two- or more dimensional. At the bifurcation point, the fixed point changes its stability and a new limit cycle arises.

4 Numerical approach to identifying bifurcations

4.1 Bifurcation diagrams

Bifurcation diagrams are curves that shows the value of a fixed point \mathbf{x}^* and its stability (whether stable or unstable) as a function of the parameter value p (Examples of bifurcation diagrams are shown in Fig. 1 a, b, c (bottom row), and d). Bifurcation diagrams provides an intuitive way to visualize how parameter changes lead to bifurcations and thus study the behavior of the system at different parameter values. When analytically computing bifurcation diagrams becomes difficult especially for higher dimensional dynamical systems, we require a numerical approach to track the value and stability of fixed points as we vary the parameter value.

For finding the fixed points of a continuous dynamical system, one can search for the solution for $f(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ using a numerical solver (for example the Newton's method which will be discussed later), while varying the

value of parameter p ². One can search for the solutions of $f(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ for a grid of initial conditions \mathbf{x}_0 for several values of p . However, this approach would become quickly infeasible for high-dimensional systems since the number of initial conditions to be specified to cover the state space would increase exponentially with the number of dimensions D and so does the required computational time. Therefore we require a smarter way to track the fixed points when the parameter p changes.

4.2 Continuation analysis

Continuation analysis provides us with a method to track the fixed points when changing the system parameter p without combing through the complete state space with a grid of initial conditions. A simple approach for tracking the fixed points with changing parameter p would be to vary the value of p and solve for $f(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ starting from an initial condition \mathbf{x}_0 . However, this would allow us to find only a single fixed point \mathbf{x}^* for a particular p value (as the numerical solver algorithm would converge to one fixed point in the vicinity of the initial condition \mathbf{x}_0). If there are multiple fixed points for the same p value, this would be ignored. For example, in a saddle-node bifurcation (Fig. 1a), each parameter value $p > 0$ has two fixed points $\mathbf{x}^* = \pm\sqrt{p}$, but depending on where the initial condition \mathbf{x}_0 is set, the simple approach defined above converges to only one of these fixed points. To prevent this, continuation method performs an optimization in a mixed state-parameter space $\mathbf{z} = (\mathbf{x}, p)$. One can then rewrite the dynamical system in the mixed parameter space as $h(\mathbf{z}) = f(\mathbf{x}, p)$ and continuation process looks for the solutions for $h(\mathbf{z}) = 0$ ³. To this end, continuation uses a two-step process known as the predictor-corrector process (Fig. ??) given by

$$\mathbf{z}_m^* = (\mathbf{x}_m^*(p_m), p_m) \xrightarrow{\text{predictor}} \hat{\mathbf{z}} = (\hat{\mathbf{x}}, p) \xrightarrow{\text{corrector}} \mathbf{z}_{m+1}^* = (\mathbf{x}_{m+1}^*(p_{m+1}), p_{m+1}). \quad (7)$$

$\mathbf{z}_m^* = (\mathbf{x}_m^*(p_m), p_m)$ specifies the fixed point \mathbf{x}_m^* located in the m -th iteration of continuation process and the corresponding parameter value of p_m . The predictor generates a guess $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ for the next iteration based on the fixed points and parameters identified in previous iterations. An example is a secant predictor which estimates $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ as a linear extrapolation of two previously found solutions \mathbf{z}_m^* and \mathbf{z}_{m-1}^* as

$$\hat{\mathbf{z}} = \mathbf{z}_m^* + \sigma_m(\mathbf{z}_m^* - \mathbf{z}_{m-1}^*) \quad (8)$$

where σ_m is the step-length of the predictor which can be varied to adjust the resolution of the found solutions. Starting from $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$, a corrector solve for $h(\mathbf{z}) = 0$ to get the next solution \mathbf{z}^{m+1} . This can be done iteratively using the Newton's method [Datseris and Parlitz, 2022]

$$\mathbf{z}_{j+1} = \mathbf{z}_j + \delta_j J_h^{-1}(\mathbf{z}_j) h(\mathbf{z}_j) \quad (9)$$

$$\text{with } h(\mathbf{z}) = (f_1(\mathbf{x}, p), \dots, f_D(\mathbf{x}, p)), \quad J_h(z) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_1} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_D} & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial p} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial f_D}{\partial x_1} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_D}{\partial x_D} & \frac{\partial f_D}{\partial p} \end{bmatrix}$$

where j is the iteration, $J_h(\mathbf{z}_j)^{-1}$ is the inverse of the Jacobian of $h(\mathbf{z})$ at $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{z}_j$ and δ_j is a damping factor or corrector step-length. The Newton's method solves for $h(\mathbf{z}) = 0$ starting at an initial condition \mathbf{z}_0 (in our case $\mathbf{z}_0 = \hat{\mathbf{z}}$ which is the predictor's guess) by iteratively updating the value of \mathbf{z} in the direction of steepest descent of the function $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ at the current iteration until $\|h(\mathbf{z}) - 0\|$ is less than a specified tolerance. The damping factor or corrector step-length dictates the number of steps required to reach a solution. Too small step lengths may lead to a large number of unwanted steps whereas too large step lengths can lead to the algorithm overlooking the solution or bouncing back and forth near a solution without actually converging to the solution. As a rule of thumb, if the current iteration $j + 1$ leads to a suboptimal solution compared

²For discrete dynamical systems, the fixed points can be located by finding the solution to the equation $g(\mathbf{x}) = f(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{x} = 0$ using same numerical solver algorithms

³For discrete dynamical systems, one can write $h(\mathbf{z}) = f(\mathbf{x}, p) - \mathbf{x}$

to previous solution j , that is if $\|h(\mathbf{z}_{j+1})\| \geq \|h(\mathbf{z}_j)\|$, one should continue from iteration j with a reduced damping factor [Datseris and Parlitz, 2022].

However, the system of equations defined in Eqn. 9 consists of D equations (elements of $h(\mathbf{z})$) and $D + 1$ unknowns (D elements of state vector \mathbf{x} and parameter p). To resolve this, we can add a $D + 1$ -th element to expand $h(\mathbf{z})$. This can be done by specifying that the k -th element in \mathbf{z} should take a particular value η in the next iteration of continuation. Since the Newton's method searches for zero of each element in $h(\mathbf{z})$, this condition can be added to the optimization problem by setting $h_{D+1}(\mathbf{z}) = z_k - \eta$. Thus we have

$$h(\mathbf{z}) = \begin{pmatrix} f_1(\mathbf{x}, p) \\ \vdots \\ f_D(\mathbf{x}, p) \\ z_k - \eta \end{pmatrix}, \quad J_h(z) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_1} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_D} & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial p} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial f_D}{\partial x_1} & \cdots & \frac{\partial f_D}{\partial x_D} & \frac{\partial f_D}{\partial p} \\ \delta_{1,k} & \cdots & \cdots & \delta_{D+1,k} \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where $\delta_{i,j}$ is the Kronecker's delta, which is one only when $i = j$ and zero otherwise. Therefore, only the k -th element in the $D + 1$ -th row of $J_h(\mathbf{z})$ is one. At each continuation iteration m , the index k is chosen as the index of the element of z with the maximum relative change from the previous iteration [Seydel, 2009]. That is,

$$k = \arg \max\{\Delta_r z_1, \dots, \Delta_r z_{D+1}\} \quad (11)$$

with $\Delta_r z_i = \|z_i^m - z_i^{m-1}\|/\|z_i^m\|$. The value of η can be chosen as [Seydel, 2009],

$$\eta = z_k^m + \zeta(z_k^m - z_k^{m-1}) \quad (12)$$

where ζ is an adjustable factor or step length. A detailed discussion on how to choose the step length is given section 4.7 in [Seydel, 2009]. With the additional element in $h(\mathbf{z})$, we now have a system of $D + 1$ equations and $D + 1$ unknowns which can be solved using the Newton's method given in Eqn. 9 by plugging in $h(\mathbf{z})$ and $J_h(\mathbf{z})$ from Eqn. 10. Starting at an initial condition $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$, the Newton's method converges to nearest fixed point $\mathbf{z}_m^* = (\mathbf{x}_m^*, p_m)$.

Once the fixed point \mathbf{x}_m^* is found, one can compute the stability of the found fixed point based on the eigenvalues of the Jacobian J_f of $f(\mathbf{x})$ at $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_m^*$ by using the linearized stability analysis discussed in section 2 of this document. If the stability property of the fixed point changes from one continuation iteration to another, a bifurcation has been identified. Additionally, if the fixed point becomes unstable and its eigenvalues have a non-zero imaginary part, a Hopf bifurcation has been identified [Datseris and Parlitz, 2022].

An important practical consideration for the continuation process is that the predictor would not be able to provide an initial guess until the second iteration, since it requires the solutions of two previous iterations. Therefore, to start the continuation process, one need to provide an initial condition $\mathbf{z}_0 = (\mathbf{x}_0, p_0)$ for the first iteration. Once the first iteration converges to a solution $\mathbf{z}_1^* = (\mathbf{x}_1^*, p_1)$, one need to provide $\Delta \mathbf{z}_1^*$ for the predictor to generate an initial guess $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ for the second iteration. After the second iteration, the continuation process can continue automatically using the predictor-corrector process described in section 4.2. The process can be continued until the parameter value goes beyond a specified range of relevant parameter values.

Since the continuation process searches for fixed points in the mixed state-parameter space (\mathbf{x}, p) , it is able to find multiple fixed points for the same parameter value p during the continuation process if these fixed points all lie on the same branch of the bifurcation diagram (as in the case of saddle-node bifurcations, Fig. 1a). However, if the bifurcation diagram has multiple branches (as in the case of pitchfork bifurcation, Fig. 1c), one need to start at different initial conditions to find all the branches of the bifurcation diagram.

4.3 Two-parameter problem

Section 4.2 deals with finding the bifurcation diagrams of continuous dynamical systems $f(\mathbf{x}, p)$ with a single parameter, p . In this section, we are interested in studying the bifurcations in dynamical systems $f(\mathbf{x}, a, b)$

with two parameters, a and b . Let us consider an example of a simple 1D continuous dynamical system with two parameters,

$$\dot{x} = f(x) = ax + x^3 + b \quad (13)$$

where a and b are the parameters and x is the state variable. Fig. 7 shows the bifurcation diagram for this system for different values of a and b . One can identify that the bifurcation point (point at which the fixed point changes its stability) changes its position based on the value of the two parameters. In the two-parameter problem, we are interested in tracking how the bifurcation point changes when two parameters vary together.

Figure 2: The bifurcation diagram of system specified in Eqn. 13 for different values of b . The bifurcation point changes with the value of b .

One can apply the continuation process described in section 4.2 to two-parameter problem with some modification. Since we are interesting in the bifurcation points in the two parameter problem, we need a device to track the bifurcation points. Since the Jacobian evaluated at the fixed point is singular ($rank J_f(\mathbf{x}^*) = D - 1$ [Seydel, 2009]), the determinant of the Jacobian J_f evaluated at fixed point is zero. One can incorporate this condition into the system of equations being solved by the Newton's method to obtain the bifurcation point as a solution. The Newton's method then solves the extended system of equations in the mixed state-parameter space $\mathbf{z} = (\mathbf{x}, a, b)$

$$h(\mathbf{z}) = \begin{pmatrix} f(\mathbf{x}, a, b) \\ J_f(\mathbf{x}, a, b) \end{pmatrix} = 0 \quad (14)$$

Since we now have two parameters (thus leading to $D + 1$ equations and $D + 2$ unknowns), we need to expand the system of equations with an additional element. One can follow a similar procedure described in section 4.2 and set the k -th element of \mathbf{z} to be a specific value η . Thus the system of equations becomes

$$h(\mathbf{z}) = \begin{pmatrix} f(\mathbf{x}, a, b) \\ J_f(\mathbf{x}, a, b) \\ z_k - \eta \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} f_1(\mathbf{x}, a, b) \\ \vdots \\ f_D(\mathbf{x}, a, b) \\ J_f(\mathbf{x}, a, b) \\ z_k - \eta \end{pmatrix} = 0 \quad (15)$$

With this extended system of equations, one can directly apply the continuation process with predictor-corrector iterations to track the bifurcation points in the two-dimensional parameter space. However, the method specified here is limited to small D since the determinant of J_f needs to be computed analytically for applying Newton's method.

4.4 Software implementation

In this project, I implemented the continuation analysis for tracking the fixed points of one-parameter dynamical systems and bifurcation points of two-parameter dynamical systems in the parameter space. Python was used for implementation along with a suite of commonly available packages like Numpy, Scipy, Sympy, and Matplotlib. The software implementation is available in Github.

4.5 Results

Finally, the continuation process was applied to generate the bifurcation diagrams for some canonical one- and two-parameter systems. In this section, some results of the continuation analysis are presented and compared with the benchmark approach of searching through the complete state space using a grid of initial conditions for a range of parameter values (mentioned in section 3).

4.5.1 Saddle-node bifurcation

Fig. 3 shows the bifurcation diagram for a saddle-node bifurcation in a simple 1D continuous dynamical system. The continuation approach could track the fixed points and their stability and gives similar results as that of the benchmark approach. The bifurcation occurs at $p = 0$ which is identified by both the benchmark and continuation approach. It can also be seen that the continuation approach could find the fixed points on both sides of x for the same parameter value p .

Figure 3: Bifurcation diagram depicting a saddle-node bifurcation in a 1D dynamical system given by $\dot{x} = x^2 - p$. (a) Benchmark approach, (b) Continuation approach.

4.5.2 Supercritical pitchfork bifurcation

Fig. 4 shows the bifurcation diagram for a supercritical pitchfork bifurcation in a 1D continuous dynamical system $\dot{x} = px - x^3$. The complete bifurcation diagram has two branches. A single run of continuation process leads to either of these branches based on the specified initial condition. To obtain both the branches, the continuation process has to be run multiple times with different initial conditions.

Figure 4: Bifurcation diagram depicting a supercritical pitchfork bifurcation in a 1D dynamical system given by $\dot{x} = px - x^3$. (a) Benchmark approach, (b) Continuation approach with initial condition at $x_0 = 1, p = 1$, (c) Continuation approach with initial condition at $x_0 = 0, p = 1$, (d) Two runs of continuation approach with initial conditions specified in (b) and (c).

4.5.3 Fitzhugh-Nagumo model

Fitzhugh-Nagumo model is a simplified model of a spiking neuron which can be formulated as a two-dimensional dynamical system [Datseris and Parlitz, 2022]

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{u} &= au(u - b)(1 - u) - w + I \\ \dot{w} &= \varepsilon(u - w) \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

where u is the cell membrane voltage and w is the recovery variable, I is the magnitude of stimulus current, ε control the rate of change of w , and a and b are the parameters of the system which decides the stability of the fixed points. The recovery variable w has a much slower dynamics than u and this is achieved by setting the value of ε to low. To simplify the parameter space, we set $I = 0$, $\varepsilon = 0.001$. Depending on the values of a and b , the system can reach different regimes like excitable, bistable and oscillatory as shown in Fig. 5.

The continuation analysis was applied to the Fitzhugh-Nagumo model by setting value of b to be 0.2 and varying the value of a thus making it a one-parameter problem of a 2D dynamical system. The results are shown in Fig. 6. Again, the complete bifurcation diagram (obtained by benchmark approach) contains two branches and the continuation run finds either of these branches depending on the initial condition. Therefore, two continuation runs were applied with different initial conditions to obtain both the branches.

4.5.4 Two-parameter problem

For the two-parameter problem, the simple 1D system in Eqn 13 with two parameters a and b was considered. The continuation process finds the bifurcation points in a two-dimensional parameter space. The results are shown in Fig. 7 and are similar to the results reported in the literature [Seydel, 2009]. Importantly, the optimization in the mixed state-parameter space allowed a single continuation run to track the complete bifurcation diagram. That is, the continuation process could track the bifurcation points on both sides of b for the same value of a .

Figure 5: (a) State space of the Fitzhugh-Nagumo model (Eqn. 16) for $a = 3, b = 0.2, I = 0$ and $\varepsilon = 0.001$. The green dotted curve shows the u -nullcline and orange dashed curve shows the w -nullcline and the intersection of the nullclines at $(0,0)$ is a stable fixed point for these parameter values. (b) Since a perturbation above $u = 0.21, w = 0$ (for example, due to an external current I) leads to an excursion through the state space as depicted by the red curve before returning to the fixed point at $(0,0)$, the system is said to be in an excitable regime. (c) For parameter values $a = 8, b = 0.2, I = 0$ and $\varepsilon = 0.001$, the nullclines intersect at three fixed points, two of which are stable, thus making the system bistable. (d) For $a = 3, b = -0.05, I = 0$ and $\varepsilon = 0.001$, the fixed point at $(0,0)$ becomes unstable and a stable limit cycle arises (blue curve) and the system is said to be in an oscillatory regime. Figure from [Datseris and Parlitz, 2022].

Figure 6: Bifurcation diagram depicting the fixed points and their stability for a Fitzhugh-Nagumo model (Eqn. 16) when varying the parameter a (Other parameters have fixed values: $b = 0.2, \varepsilon = 0.001, I = 0$). (a) Results from benchmark approach, (b) Continuation approach with initial condition $u_0 = 0, w_0 = 0, a_0 = 0$ and initial step $\Delta u_0 = 0, \Delta w_0 = 0, \Delta a_0 = 0.01$. (c) Continuation approach with initial condition $u_0 = 1, w_0 = 1, a_0 = 10$ and initial step $\Delta u_0 = -0.02, \Delta w_0 = -0.02, \Delta a_0 = -1$. (d) Two runs of continuation with initial conditions and initial steps specified in (b) and (c).

5 Conclusion

In this project, the continuation analysis for tracking fixed points, their stability and bifurcations through the parameter space was implemented. Continuation approach could generate bifurcation diagrams for one- and two-dimensional systems with a single parameter and a one-dimensional system with two-parameters. A generic software package has been implemented which could be applied for bifurcation analysis of any general one- or two-dimensional systems with one or two parameters.

5.1 Limitations

Since complete bifurcation diagrams may contain multiple branches [Datseris and Parlitz, 2022], it is required to run the continuation process several times with different initial conditions. However, it is difficult to define good initial conditions so that all branches are found. If the possible branches could not be guessed, one may

Figure 7: Bifurcation points for a 1D dynamical system $\dot{x} = ax + x^3 + b$ with two parameters, a and b . (a) Results obtained by applying the continuation process to the two-parameter problem as described in section 4.3. (b) Results reported in literature [Seydel, 2009].

randomly define many initial conditions in the state space and rely on a little bit of luck [Seydel, 2009] to find all branches. Similarly, the decisions on initial step and step lengths of predictor and corrector can affect the solutions. Since continuation process calculates discrete points (rather than a smooth curve) in the state-parameter space, interpolating the curve through these points can lead to misleading results especially when points belonging to different branches are connected [Seydel, 2009]. Oftentimes, the continuation process can itself result in branch jumping [Seydel, 2009], when it reaches to solutions in a different branch than continuing in the same branch (see [Seydel, 2009] section 4.9).

The continuation process is implemented here only for continuous dynamical systems. However, the general idea is also applicable to discrete dynamical systems (by solving for $h(\mathbf{z}) = (f(\mathbf{x}, p) - \mathbf{x}, z_k - \eta) = 0$ using the predictor-corrector process). Similarly, the continuation process described here can be used for bifurcation analysis of systems with less than or equal to two parameters. For higher parameter problems, one would need to define more equations in $h(\mathbf{z})$ which is out of scope of this work.

5.2 Future work

Since the basic framework of continuation process has been implemented during this project, it can be applied to many real-world dynamical systems to analyse the bifurcations in those systems. The analysis here was limited to one- or two-dimensional systems with one parameter and one-dimensional system with two parameters. Next step would be to apply the implemented analysis to track bifurcations in a two-dimensional system with two parameters (for example, Fitzhugh-Nagumo model with both a and b varying) before moving to other higher dimensional systems. Similarly, a comparison of computational complexity-accuracy trade off of the continuation approach with the benchmark approach might help in allocating the computing resources more wisely. Additionally, one could also apply some techniques to control the step length factor to increase the resolution of the results where it is relevant (for example, near bifurcation points).

References

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